

**STRATEGIES FOR MANAGING DRUGS AND SUBSTANCE ABUSE
AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN KENYA:
A CASE OF ELDORET TOWN**

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Abstract:

Managing of drugs and substance abuse among students in secondary school is vital as one of the national goals of education in Kenya is to provide for the development of knowledge, skills and attitudes that will enhance acquisition of sound moral values and help children grow-up into self-disciplined, self-reliant and integrated citizens. The study assessed the strategies being used to manage drugs and substance abuse among students in secondary schools within Eldoret town and its environs. The study identified the types of drugs and substances commonly abused, the reasons and effects for abuse and the effectiveness of the strategies being used to manage the menace. The study was guided by the Social cognitive learning theory by Albert Bandura, which states that behavior is determined by the environment and a person's thought processes and pattern of actions. The study utilized descriptive research design. The study adopted both probability and non-probability sampling techniques to determine sample size. The target population of the study comprised of principals, guidance counseling masters and teachers of Christian religious education. Stratified sampling technique was applied to get eight different schools from the area of study; purposive sampling was used to select eight Principals, eight teachers of Guidance and counseling and sixteen teachers of Christian Religious Education while two hundred and twenty form four students were randomly selected to participate in the study. Quantitative Data was

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collected by use of questionnaires, while interview schedules were employed for qualitative data. Descriptive statistics was utilized to analyze quantitative data; while qualitative data was classified into themes based on the objectives of the study. The results indicated that all the strategies used to manage drugs and substance abuse in secondary schools are effective to some degree and that a combination of various strategies is what is required to have a positive impact. There is need for all stakeholders to consistently review, support and apply different strategies to reduce drugs and substance abuse among the students in secondary schools in Kenya.

Keywords: drug and substance abuse, strategies, Christian religious education

1. Introduction

The World Health Organization (2013) defines substance abuse as the harmful or hazardous use of psychoactive substances, including alcohol and illicit drugs. It includes psychoactive substances that can lead to dependence syndrome - a cluster of behavioural, cognitive, and physiological phenomena that develop after repeated substance use and that typically include a strong desire to take the drug, difficulties in controlling its use, persisting in its use despite harmful consequences, a higher priority given to drug use than to other activities and obligations, increased tolerance, and sometimes a physical withdrawal state (WHO, 2013).

According to United Nations Office on drugs and crime (2013), the global drug use situation has remained stable. While there has been some increase in the estimated total number of users of any illicit substance, estimates show that the number of drug users with dependence or drug use disorders has remained stable. The increase in the annually estimated number of users is, to a large extent, a reflection of an increase in the world population.

The abuse of drugs and substances and use of other illegal drugs can be detrimental to the health of the user. Further, the use of drugs and alcohol is not conducive to an academic atmosphere. Drug use can impede the learning process and can cause disruption for other students and disturb their academic interests. The use of alcohol or drugs in the workplace may also impede the employee's ability to perform in a safe and effective manner, and may result in injuries to others (UNODC, 2013). Furthermore, case studies around the world have reported on the problem of drug abuse among adolescents and the youth. The risk of moving to hard drugs has been found to be more than hundred times higher for persons who have smoked marijuana

at least once in their lives than those who have not (United States Department of Health and Human Services, 2005; 2007; 2009).

In Kenya, more than 22.7 % of primary and secondary children have taken alcohol, a figure that rises to about 68% for University students (Siringi, 2003). A large number of students across all age groups have been exposed to alcohol, tobacco, miraa, glue sniffing, bhang and even hard drugs such as heroin and cocaine (ibid). The National Baseline survey on drug and substance abuse among the youth in Kenya shows that up to 30% of the university students chew miraa (ibid).

In a speech delivered during the official closing of African Convention of Principals (ACP) in Kenya on 27th August 2004, the then Minister for Education, the late Honorable George Saitoti noted that, one of the root causes of some indiscipline cases in institutions could be traced to drug and substance abuse. For this reason, the war against drugs and substance abuse was one that Kenya could not afford to lose because failure to address this problem, could lead to the destruction of Kenyan youth and thus the future of the country (The East African Standard, 2004). He appealed to all to join to fight this menace.

Factors leading to initial drug use in secondary school students include curiosity, enjoyment, peer group pressure, conflict with parents, academic pressure, loneliness, and to a minor extent fatigue. The periods from 10 to 17 years of age are extremely important in adolescent psychology. These are the same periods that children make a transition from primary to secondary education, and from secondary to post-secondary institutions, and consequently have anxieties of academic success because they are exposed to extreme pressure from peers and parents, thus making them vulnerable to taking drugs.

1.1 Statement of the problem

As Kenya strives to be a Middle income economy by the year 2030, there is need for the youthful population to be well equipped with knowledge and life skills to achieve this dream. According to the World Population review (2013), 42.3% of the population of Kenya was aged between 11 and 14. These groups of youth is in the process of maturing and often face the challenging transition to independent living and adulthood therefore requiring adult guidance, support systems and relevant education to help them appropriately integrate into society. Without this guidance, they are likely to face poor job prospects, experience lifelong dependence on social service systems, use illicit drugs, become involved in the underage justice system, and become teen parents (Alliance for Excellent Education, 2003).

Youthfulness presents some very special problems and considerations. This is the period of adolescence which is full of many challenges such as stress of physiological and physical change, competition in school and life in general, generation gap, unjust and cruel world among other problems. Psychologically, the adolescents have serious developmental tasks to handle such as peer identification and individualization from their family. Sexual identification, societal and vocational role identification and negotiating issues of authority, power and independence are primary (Oketch, 2008). Therefore, there is need for more of the youth to complete their education by being drug-abuse free.

A study by Oketch (2008) revealed that drug abuse causes poor performance as 30% agreed that their colleagues who abuse drugs develop hostile behaviour. The findings appear to agree with Blandford (1998) who noted that drug abuse has become a stumbling block to the students learning behavior which is a crucial element in educational progression. Ten percent (10%) of the students believed that drug abuse contributes to withdrawal syndrome, while 8% believed that drug users are hostile.

The results imply that drug abuse to students is tantamount to poor performance as the objectives of education to students are over run by aggressive behaviour, violence and withdrawal. It becomes impossible for such students to concentrate on studies or even interact with fellow students or teachers and grow to contribute to the community, family and economy at one hundred percent. Support for prevention programs from educators and tax payers alike might be forth coming if they realized that prevention programs also contribute to academic achievement hence the need to carry an assessment on the strategies being used to manage drug and substance abuse among students in secondary schools in Kenya.

Some of these strategies have been implemented by the Ministry of Education. There is infusion of content on emerging social issues such as drugs and substance abuse in various subjects including Christian Religious Education in the school curriculum. But since the problem of drug abuse continues to be a menace in society, it is necessary to find out whether these strategies, including the teaching of Christian Religious Education in anyway helps to shape the behavior of the youth in a positive way so as to reduce the problem of drugs and substance abuse.

It is evident that the impact of drug and substance abuse on the academic performance of students in secondary school has not been fully addressed and the strategies to help rehabilitate students need to be enhanced. Alcohol and drug abuse are a major public health problem in secondary schools and this study is undertaken, to find out what the school administration are doing to reduce drug and substance abuse and, hence reveal what else needs to be done to save the youth in secondary schools. It

is true that while substance abuse is a problem that affects academic, personal and professional life seriously, it is also a treatable problem that is why there is need to reassess strategies in use and keep improving on them.

1.2 Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to assess the strategies for managing drug and substance abuse among students in secondary schools in Eldoret town and its environs.

1.3 Specific objectives of the study

- 1 To identify the types of drugs and substances commonly abused by students in secondary school in Eldoret town and its environs.
- 2 To determine the reasons for drug and substance abuse among students in secondary schools in Eldoret town.
- 3 To establish the effects of drugs and substance abuse on students' performance.
- 4 To assess the role of Christian Religious Education as a strategy to manage drugs and substance abuse among students in Secondary schools in Eldoret Town.
- 5 To assess other strategies used by School administrators to deal with drug and substance abuse among their students.

1.4 Research Questions

1. What types of drugs and substance are commonly abused by students in secondary schools in Eldoret town?
2. What are the reasons for drug and substance abuse among students in secondary schools in Eldoret town?
3. What are the effects of drug and substance abuse on students' performance?
4. What role does Christian Religious Education play as a strategy of managing drug and substance abuse among students in secondary schools?
5. How effective are the strategies used by school administration in dealing with drug and substances abuse among students?

1.5 Rationale of the Study

Kenya like many other developing countries has limited resources to cover the basic needs for her people. Abuse of drugs among the youth not only drains the economy (through trying to control the supply and demand) but also deals a blow to the country as her youth become less productive. The overall picture on drug abuse shows a steady upward trend in drug peddling as attested by seizure statistics (Mbogo, 2003).

The system of Education is a tool meant to shape the youth of this country to be whole and productive. The Objective of preventive education is to reduce or delay the likelihood of experimentation with drugs by providing information about the dangers of their use and misuse, as well as to reduce the stigma attached to alcohol and drug abuse, and encourage those who are experiencing problems to get the help they need. Drug education should ensure that pupils acquire age and context-appropriate knowledge and skills in order for them to adopt and maintain life skills and behavior that will protect them from drug abuse and dependency.

1.6 Significance of the Study

The findings of the study will be useful in guiding the Educators in reviewing the secondary school curriculum so as to integrate and infuse information on drug and substance abuse at the appropriate levels. According to Ballard, et.al, (1987), drug education should be provided before problematic behavioral patterns become established and more resistant to change, hence, there is a definite need to have a survey on the various strategies used by schools to manage drug and substance abuse among the students.

The Church and Non-governmental organizations and or individuals that are interested in helping students who abuse drugs substances and can use the information obtained in order to plan, strategize and deal with the problem where possible. In conclusion, this study will offer future researchers with the baseline information for further research in reducing the problem abuse among the youth in the nation of Kenya.

1.7 Theoretical framework

The study was guided by the Social cognitive subcategory of cognitive theory that focuses on the effects that others have on behavior by Bandura (1994). Bandura (2001) notes that any factor that influences choice behavior can profoundly affect the direction of personal development. This is because the social influences operating in selected environments continue to promote certain competencies, values, and interests long after the decisional determinant has rendered its inaugurating effect. Bandura (2001) states that, *“The rapid speed of informational, social, and technological dynamism is placing a premium on personal efficacy for self-development and self-renewal throughout the life course”*. These informational, social and technological changes provide motivation and drive the desire to learn in people. Efficacy beliefs are the foundation of human agency. Unless people believe they can produce desired results and forestall detrimental ones by their actions, they have little incentive to act or to persevere in the face of difficulties (Bandura, 2009).

Instrumental learners are also a form of learning theory. This theory is based on the following principles, which can be used to define social cognitive theory. Firstly, that people learn by observing others, a process known as vicarious learning, not only through their own direct experiences. Secondly, that although learning can modify behavior, people do not always apply what they have learned. Individual choice is based on perceived or actual consequences of behavior. Thirdly, that people are more likely to follow the behaviors modeled by someone with whom they can identify. The more perceived commonalities and/or emotional attachments between the observer and the model, the more likely the observer will learn from the model. Finally, the degree of self-efficacy that a learner possesses directly affects his or her ability to learn. Self-efficacy is a fundamental belief in one's ability to achieve a goal.

It is therefore important to adopt the social cognitive learning and liberal feminism theories because they both capture the need for individual independence and growth, notwithstanding the environmental factors that may obstruct their objectives. Thus, the need to assess the strategy used to manage drugs substance among students in Secondary so as to help the youth to develop strong positive characters (Bandura, 2001).

1.8 Conceptual framework

The conceptual framework shows the relationship and interaction between the independent, dependent variables and the intervening variables.

Figure 1: Relationship among the independent, dependent and moderating variables

2. Summary of Literature Review

Over the past few decades, the use of illegal drugs and substances has spread at an unparalleled rate and has reached every part of the world. According to a United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) report (2005), out of some 200 million people, or 5 percent of the total world's population aged 15 - 64 have used drugs at least once in the last 12 months (during that period) an estimated 15 million people more than the 2004 estimate. The report also stated that, both the developed and developing nations have been immune to the devastating effects of drug abuse. A survey in the Czech Republic showed that 37 percent of new drug users were teenagers between 15 and 19 years old. Every country in the world, developed or developing, incurs substantial costs as a result of damages caused by substance abuse (World Drug Report, 2005). The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that 1.1 billion people, representing a third of the world population above the age of 15 years, use tobacco, principally in the form of the cigarettes. Of these smokers, 700 million of them males live in developing countries (WHO, 2005).

In an annual report, published in February 2001 by the International Narcotics Control Board (INCB) on the situation of sub-Saharan Africa: "*Western African syndicates, with their experience in smuggling cannabis and heroin, are actively looking for new connections in Latin America and are bringing cocaine trafficking to all parts of sub-Saharan Africa.*" (International Narcotics Control Board, 2001). Fatoye (2003) in his study of substance use among youths in rural and urban communities in South western Nigeria on 567 respondents, found that the most commonly used drugs and their prevalence were analgesics (48.7%), stimulants (20.9%), antibiotics (16.6%), alcohol (13.4%), hypnotic sedatives (8.9%) and tobacco (3%).

In Kenya, the documentation on drug abuse can be traced back to 1965, when a study on drug dependence on Khat was carried out (Eddy, 1965). It was found that males tended to use Khat more than females. In 1982, the department of psychiatry and community health with the help of medical students carried out a survey in Kisii district (Acuda, 1982), and noted that 27% of males and 24% females could be classified as alcoholics. The VOA (2014), in a survey of drug and substance abuse, noted that most students had formed a drinking culture. VOA's director Mr. Njeru, said that, "*People in schools are so focused on passing exams that they have actually missed out on so many other things that they can do, that can make their life rich in school, If you ask a high school kid today whether he knows any art gallery in Nairobi, he'll tell you he doesn't know. But he knows all the pubs, all the leading pubs, he can count for you, there are 20, 30, 40 different pubs in the city and tell you the best days and times even on weekdays to visit*".

According to The Standard (2014), while addressing a group of secondary school students on an educational tour in Naivasha at a meeting in regards to recent deaths of illicit brew drinkers, Mr. Mututho revealed that students were increasingly developing devious means to peddle and use drugs in schools. He cited a case of a school in Murang'a where dealers cleverly send students drugs across a river that passes by the institution and in Kirinyaga, the chairman of the National Campaign Against Drug Abuse (Nacada), John Mututho, wanted a liquor outlet that sold alcohol to students in Kirinyaga County shutdown as according to reports, four schools girls went to the Wines and Spirits outlet, bought alcohol and started to drink. Mututho ordered for the arrest and prosecution of the owner of the business for breaching the alcohol rule (The Standard, 2014).

3. Methodology

3.1 Research design

The research design was descriptive in nature. A descriptive research design determines and reports the way things are. This is in agreement with Kothari (2008). The design also provided enough protection against biasness and helped maximize reliability.

The study involved collection of both qualitative and quantitative data. Quantitative research is linked to interpretive paradigm. It enables the researcher to describe a distribution of scores or measurements using a few statistics. The researcher chose to use qualitative research in situations where it was felt that quantitative measures could not adequately describe or interpret a situation in relation to drug abuse among students. Quantitative research is linked to positivism whereby reality is seen as "*stable, observable and measurable*" (Creswell, 2003). Quantitative research seeks causal determination, prediction, and generalization of findings. It focuses on collecting numeric data which is then analyzed statistically.

3.2 Sampling methods and size

For the purposes of getting a representative sample, the researcher stratified schools in Eldoret town and its environs into school types (public and private) and also into boarding, day, single-sex and co-educational. Eight out of the twenty five schools in the town were selected for participation in this study. All Principals, Guidance and counselors and Christian Religious Education teachers from the selected schools automatically qualified for inclusion in this study through purposive sampling. 30% of the form four students were selected through simple random sampling. Table 1 indicates how the total number of schools for the study was arrived at.

Table 1: Sampling frame

School category		Population	No.	Sample (30%)	Sample (30%)
Public	Girls only	Boarding	5	2	2
		Day	0	0	
	Boys only	Boarding	4	1.2	1
		Day	0	0	
	Co-educational	Boarding	0	0	2
		Day	6	1.8	
Boarding & Day		2	1	1	
Private	Girls only	Boarding	4	1.2	1
		Day	0	0	
	Boys Only	Boarding	4	1.2	1
		Day	0		
Total			25		8

3.3 Research Instruments

Data was collected with the use of questionnaires and interview schedules. The questionnaires had matrix questions so that the respondents who may be victims may not be put off and it would also be easy to compare the responses given to different items. Likert scale was necessary when evaluating the effectiveness of the Educational programmes with regard to their contribution to the fight against drug and substance abuse in secondary schools. Interview schedules were organized with the heads of the institutions (Principals).

3.4 Data Analysis Technique

Data was analyzed quantitatively and qualitatively. Quantitative data was analyzed by frequency tables and percentages using Statistical Program for Social Scientists (SPSS) for windows version 19.0. Frequency tables represent the most commonly used method in presenting data in descriptive research (Kathuri & Pals, 1993). Qualitative data was classified into logical thematic categories based on the objectives and then coded. Analysis of qualitative data was collected using interviews and document analysis was utilized for an ongoing process where emerging themes were categorized based on the research questions.

3.5 Ethical Considerations

The interviewer sought for official permission to carry out the research from concerned authorities. Informed consent was also sought during the actual administration of the research instruments according to guidelines in research ethics. The interviewer explained the aim and objective of the study in order to remove doubt hence avoid any

misconception and poor attitude among respondents. It was also prudent to assure the respondents of total confidentiality of information sought. In this case the names of the respondents were not necessary; they remained anonymous. The research findings were revealed after completing the study. It is hoped that they will be useful in reviewing of the education policies in the county with regard to the teaching of Christian Religious Education in Secondary schools in Kenya.

4. Summary of Findings, Conclusions and Recommendations

4.1 Types of drugs abused

The study sought to identify the types of drugs and substances commonly abused by secondary school students in Eldoret Town and its environs, to achieve this several variables were looked at as illustrated in table 2. Figure 2 shows Principals' and Guidance and counselors' view on type of drugs abused.

Table 2: Types of drugs abused

	Very Often		Often		Not Often		Not all	
	fre	%	fre	%	fre	%	Fre	%
Alcohol(Beer)	40	18.2	22	7.7	0	0	158	74.1
Tobacco	8	2.7	0	0	161	79.1	40	18.2
Narcotics	26	3.3	0	0	0	0	0	97.7
Cannabis	26	8.1	0	0.5	0	0	200	91.4
Heroin	0	0	0	0	0	0	220	100
Mandrax	0	0	0	0	0	0	220	100

Figure 2: Principals', Guidance, and counselors' view on type of drugs abused

4.2 Reasons for drug and substance abuse

The study found out that the main reasons why students abuse drugs is mainly contributed by peer pressure. Further reasons are that the drugs and substances are easily found in the environment, and curiosity. Majority of the students abuse drugs away from their parents supervision. Data was collected to determine the reasons why students in secondary schools in Eldoret town and its environs abuse drugs and other substances. Their responses are illustrated in table 3.

Table 3: Reasons for Students Abuse of Drugs

Reasons for drug & substance abuse	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Curiosity	55(25%)	165(75%)	0	0	0
Drugs are easy to get	17 (8.0%)	158(72%)	45 (20%)	0	8.7
To perform better	24 (10.9%)	2 (0.5%)	0	176(80%)	13(5.5%)
Peer pressure	202 (91.8%)	18(8.2%)	0	0	0

In various studies carried out in the past that focused on the reasons for drug and substance abuse among the youth and students, it was found by NACADA (2012) that the increase in drug abuse was related to the ease of obtaining the drugs and substances. Peer pressure was also found to be a key driver to adolescents to abusing drugs (United Nations Office on Drugs and Crimes, 2003). Parental influence also contributed to youth engaging in the vice (NACADA, 2004). The report stated that young people whose parents use or sell alcohol and other drugs are likely to abuse these substances.

4.3 Effects of drugs and substance abuse on students

The researcher also sought to determine the effects of drug and substance abuse on the academic performance of students who abuse them. The responses are indicated in table 4.

Table 4: Effects of Drug and Substance Abuse on Student's academic performance

Effects of abusing drugs	Strongly Agreed		Agreed		Undecided		Disagreed		Strongly disagreed	
	G&C F (%)	Stu F (%)	G&C F (%)	Stu F (%)	G&C F (%)	Stu F (%)	G&C F (%)	Stu F (%)	G&C F (%)	Stu F (%)
Absenteeism	5(62.5)	55(25)	1(12.5)	165(75)	0	0	1(12.5)	0	1(12.5)	0
Violent /fights	4(50)	0	2(25)	165(75)	0	40(18.2)	1(12.5)	0	1(12.5)	15(6.8)

Lose interest in learning	6 (75)	22(100)	2(25)	176(80)	0	0	22(10)	0	0
Poor performance	6(75)	176(80)	2(25)	44(20)	0	0	0	0	0
Withdrawal	1(12.5)	0	6(75)	0	0	0	1(12.5)	0	0

4.4 The role of Christian Religious Education as a Strategy in Managing Drug and Substance Abuse

Christian Religious Education as a subject in secondary schools is not very helpful. This is because the content on drugs and substance abuse is taught late in form four. The teachers do not employ a variety of teaching methods to present the information in a way that can dissuade the abusers to stop. The teachers are also ill equipped in terms of availability of resources. Majority depend on information in the approved textbooks of C.R.E.

The use of Life Approach which is meant to focus on the learner, help them to respond positively is not utilized at all. According to the respondents, teachers of C.R.E do not use the approved approaches of teaching. This approach is learner centered and when used effectively, the learner is made to understand, feel concerned and make appropriate decisions which lead to positive change in behavior. Moreover, most teachers just use the Bible and C.R.E textbooks, neglecting other resources such as audio-visual and realia (example of drugs).

The teachers do not vary teaching methods to make lessons interesting, hence the role of Christian Religious Education as a strategy to minimize the abuse of drug and substance is far from being achieved. From the findings as to whether the subject is helpful and therefore be made compulsory, most of the respondents (77.8%) said that the subject does not help in changing the attitude of the learners towards drug and substance abuse yet this is a subject based on the word of God, hence it is meant to develop the spiritual and moral lives of both the teachers and students.

4.5 Other Strategies used by School Administrators to Manage Drug and Substance Abuse

Most of the school administrators rely on teachers of guidance and counseling to help students who abuse drugs and substances. They also make use of the talks on assemblies, invited experts from NACADA to create awareness on the dangers of taking drugs and substances. There is also peer counseling whereby fellow students are used to counsel their colleagues. The study sought to find out Strategies being applied in schools to prevent or minimize drug abuse in secondary schools in Eldoret town and its environs, results are illustrated in the figure 3.

Figure 3: Strategies being applied by the school administration to deal with Drug abuse in school

4.6 Conclusion

Drug and substance abuse is a problem among students in secondary schools in Eldoret town. From the findings of this study, the most commonly abuse substance include alcohol, tobacco and stimulants such as miraa. Students are mostly influenced to abuse drugs and substances due to peer pressure, curiosity and because these drugs are easily available and purchased from kiosks or shops. The students who are involved in drug and substances miss out on their lessons, skip school or engage in violent fights with others. They eventually lose interest in learning hence perform poorly in their academics.

School administrations are doing their best to help students involved in drug abuse. Although few expel such students, most of them rely on guiding and counseling and generally create awareness on the dangers of drugs and substance abuse on assemblies. The role of religious education as a strategy to manage drug and substance among students has very little impact on the lives of the students. There is no behavior change after such lessons. Moreover, the teachers also have no much faith in the subject as a tool that can be used to reduce drug abuse among students.

Most of the strategies being used to prevent, reduce or manage drug and substance abuse are effective to some degree. A combination of various strategies is what is required to have a positive impact on the students who are involved in drug and substance abuse as illustrated in figure 4. One of the Principals stated that the combination of different strategies, support programmes and interlink of various

institutions can assist in preventing and reducing drug and substance abuse in secondary schools.

Figure 4: Strategies to prevent reduce / manage drug and substance abuse

4.7 Recommendations

Based on the conclusions of this study, the following recommendations are made;

1. NACADA should take a lead in ensuring that policies on drug and substance abuse are made robust to focus on youths. There should be strict laws and penalties for those who allow school going children in their recreation places such as pubs, bars or who sell alcohol or cigarettes to them. This should be enforced by existing Legislative, Executive and Judiciary as arms of the government.
2. Students should make use of the life skills they acquire in various subjects such as Christian Religious Education, social studies and English / Swahili literature to be able to resist peer pressure and curiosity. Moreover, parents should be role models and ensure their homes and activities do not influence their children in abusing drugs.
3. School administrators, counselors in collaboration with parents should provide counseling to students suspected or found abusing drugs, rather than using extreme punitive measures such as suspension or expulsion from school or being taken to police stations. Teachers in secondary schools should also be keen when

teaching students and have an interest in those who frequently absent themselves from school, or whose continuous assessment performance reveal a downward trend. By doing so, they will help rehabilitate those already abusing drugs or refer them for guiding and counseling.

4. Guidance and counseling as a department should be strengthened in learning institutions. The Ministry of Education, Teachers Service Commission should motivate teachers who offer these services so that they can enhance their skills through seminars, resources and supportive institutions. Peer counseling should also be intensified in schools. School administrators should be able to identify and train those students who are of good character to act as peer counselors to their fellow students.
5. Kenya Institute of curriculum Development should review the Christian Religious Education syllabus with a view of making it a robust subject by adding relevant content on life-skills, change the timing when the content on drugs and substance abuse is taught from form four to form one. The Ministry of Education through the Quality Assurance Officers should supervise and give advice to teachers of Christian Religious Education on the approaches and methods of teaching the subject, encourage school administrators to buy, prepare or improvise on various resource materials which can be used to present information on drugs and substance abuse in an appealing manner and at the same time cause students to desist from abusing drugs and other substances.
6. The teachers of C.R.E should inculcate life skills to learners, be themselves role models to be able to mentor their students to be morally upright persons in the society.

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